

BIIGLE User Meeting 2023 Summary

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The BIIGLE User Meeting took place on Feb. 8, 2023 from 2 pm to 5 pm CET via Zoom. It was attended by almost 70 BIIGLE users with various affiliations.

The meeting started with an introduction by Tim Nattkemper who presented a short history of the BIIGLE project, the current state of BIIGLE and a brief outlook on important next steps for the project.

The introduction was followed by three presentations by BIIGLE users who highlighted how they and their institutes use BIIGLE for their research.

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Presentations

- 1. Coral reefs, sea mount, hydrothermal vents... an overview of BIIGLE's uses at Ifremer and subsequent analysis**

Marin Marcillat (Ifremer, France)

- 2. Using BIIGLE for Surveying Benthic Communities on an Arctic Seamount**

Heidi Meyer (IMR, Norway)

- 3. Collaboration using BIIGLE on underwater and trawl surveys by Fisheries and Oceans Canada across Arctic – Atlantic regions**

Claude Nozères (DFO, Canada)

The presentation slides are published together with this summary.

Discussion

The discussion was structured in the three loosely defined topics image/video annotation, automated annotation assistance and GIS integration, which were determined by an initial poll. After that, there was an open discussion. Several questions were asked and answered during the discussion. Some questions were only asked in written form but not answered. All questions and answers can be found in the Q/A section below. There were also several requests for new or improved features in BIIGLE. These are summarized in the Wishlist below. This section summarizes the most salient topics of the discussion.

Label versions

One point raised by Claude Nozères (DFO, Canada) was the need for a version history of label names. If the “state of the art” taxonomic name of a species changes, databases such as WoRMS retain a link to the previous name(s). In BIIGLE, a label either stays the outdated name or is changed to the new name but without any information what it was previously called. It was agreed that this is an issue that should be addressed in BIIGLE but a solution requires a more in-depth discussion. The discussion will be continued in the GitHub community forum.

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>

Export of annotations for machine learning

Several attendees discussed the need to export annotations for training datasets of machine learning algorithms. FathomNet was named as one well-known database that collects image annotations as training data.

BIIGLE offers machine-readable report files (CSV and COCO) that can be used to process annotations for machine learning. There is also a discussion about a direct interface between BIIGLE and FathomNet at GitHub.

<https://github.com/biigle/core/issues/443>

GIS integration

The BIIGLE team made clear that they will only consider the addition of GIS features to BIIGLE if they assist in the annotation process. The development will always focus on BIIGLE as an annotation tool that outputs data (as reports) for archival and further analysis.

The attendees noted that some GIS-related data could indeed assist in the annotation task if it is displayed in the annotation tool. For example, the current depth or location could help to identify objects of interest.

The display of image and video metadata (such as the depth) is already an idea on the BIIGLE roadmap. Another idea is to use video subtitles to display metadata in the video annotation tool.

<https://github.com/biigle/core/issues/462>

<https://github.com/biigle/core/issues/472>

The display of the current location is problematic. A high-resolution spatial display is only useful with detailed bathymetry, which must be provided by the users for each project. A low-resolution spatial display may not be useful for annotation. If there is any need for a continued discussion about this, it can be continued in the GitHub forum.

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>

Live video annotation

Bárbara Neves (DFO, Canada) noted that there is an interest in a live video annotation tool that can be used to review video during a ROV dive. The tool could be similar to BIIGLE's video annotation tool but with special features and assistance for a review in real time. SeaTube telepresence was suggested as an example for ROV live streams. Rachel Boschen-Rose (Marine Scotland, Scotland) and Joana Xavier (CIIMAR, Portugal) also expressed their interest in this topic.

The BIIGLE developers have already explored this idea on a technical level in the past. This knowledge could be used for the implementation of a prototype. The collaboration can only move forward as part of a joint project, as there needs to be a way to test the prototype in the field and the implementation may need additional developers. The discussion will be continued between the interested parties.

<https://github.com/biigle/core/issues/273>

Regular workshops and training

Many attendees expressed their interest in regular user meetings, workshops or training sessions for new users. This was noted by the BIIGLE team and more regular events will be held in the future.

All events will be announced through the newsletter.

<https://biigle.de/newsletter>

Community discussions and contributions at GitHub

The BIIGLE team stressed that community contributions are highly welcome at GitHub. Custom tools, scripts or solutions can be shared in the community scripts repository. The community forum is available for any kind of discussion (annotation best practices, bug reports, new features etc.). All feature ideas currently on the BIIGLE roadmap can be picked up by community developers and can be contributed via GitHub pull requests. The team is open for any kind of communication via email too (info@biigle.de).

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>

<https://github.com/biigle/community-scripts>

<https://github.com/biigle/core/blob/master/CONTRIBUTING.md>

Call for joint projects and collaboration

The BIIGLE team pointed out that the resources for BIIGLE development are currently extremely limited. There is only a single developer who also has other responsibilities beside BIIGLE development and maintenance. As a result, the implementation of most feature ideas on the BIIGLE roadmap is stalled indefinitely.

The research institutes or companies working with BIIGLE are encouraged to seek out joint projects and collaboration with the BIIGLE team (info@biigle.de) to enable the implementation of feature ideas and improve the resources that are available for active development.

Q/A

Is there a way to compare datasets in BIIGLE? If for example two analysts review the same images independently. This could be useful for training and quality.

There is currently no feature in BIIGLE to compare two sets of annotations on the same images (beside viewing the annotations in the annotation tool). The annotation session feature can be used to obtain sets of annotations (so analysts see only their own annotations). But as the focus of BIIGLE is on annotation, advanced evaluation (e.g. the estimation of inter- or intra-observer agreement) must be done externally.

There is an issue at GitHub about an inter-/intra-observer agreement report but it was not yet put onto the roadmap and needs further discussion. Any new insights on this topic could be discussed there or in the community forum.

<https://github.com/biigle/reports/issues/25>

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>

How do people interact with BIIGLE to make annotations? I expect most use mouse and keyboard, has anyone tried other methods like a stylus and tablet?

Some attendees pointed out that they used tablets (Surface, iPad) or professional digital art screens to annotate. Pen input devices are most useful for detailed polygon annotations. BIIGLE provides the polygon brush, eraser and fill instruments specifically for this use case. BIIGLE should provide first-class support for touch and pen input devices. Bug reports and ideas for improvement are welcome in the discussion forum.

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>

Can you upload image annotations not created in BIIGLE (e.g. from another annotation software or predicted labels via ML) to a volume for QA?

Is it possible to uploaded previous annotations of images back into BIIGLE?

A general bulk-upload of annotations is currently only supported via the API. There are some examples how this can be done in the community scripts repository ([annotations to biigle, regular-sampling-grid](#)). There is also a feature idea for a data import into the MAIA interface, which is designed for the review of machine learning object detections.

<https://github.com/biigle/maia/issues/95>

Furthermore, BIIGLE provides a feature for instance administrators to generate volume export files that also include annotations. These can be used to transfer volumes between different BIIGLE instances (e.g. from a temporary instance on a ship to a permanent instance of a research institute).

Could you explain why rectangle annotations sometimes cannot be validated after drawing the line to set the center axis of the rectangle?

Please get in touch via info@biigle.de or the discussion forum to describe the issue in more detail.

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>

Would it be possible to notify BIIGLE users of any updates and changes [to the software] as and when they happen?

A detailed summary of changes and new features can be found in the GitHub release notes. Currently, there is the application core and several application modules that are developed in separate repositories. The GitHub release notes also provide an RSS feed for push notifications.

<https://github.com/biigle/core/releases>

<https://github.com/biigle/maia/releases>

<https://github.com/biigle/largo/releases>

<https://github.com/biigle/sync/releases>

<https://github.com/biigle/reports/releases>

<https://github.com/biigle/geo/releases>

<https://github.com/biigle/laserpoints/releases>

<https://github.com/biigle/user-storage/releases>

The availability of larger new features will also be announced via the BIIGLE newsletter.

<https://biigle.de/newsletter>

Is there a way to add a 'scale' to video define a visual area across frames based on the distance between visible laser dots? Would help quantify annotations.

Can we take measures (e.g. corals' height) through video files using laser point detection? Or is it only possible through image files?

Laser point detection and scale information is not available for videos in BIIGLE. There is a GitHub issue about this topic but it is still up for discussion, as many videos are taken with an oblique camera angle which makes the area calculation problematic. Anyone with further insights and expertise is welcome to contribute to the issue.

<https://github.com/biigle/core/issues/269>

Would it be possible to get largo to display annotation types (e.g. polygons or points)?

There is an idea for a filtering mechanism in Largo (see issue below). Patches could be filtered by annotation shape with this mechanism. If this is not a suitable solution, please open a new discussion at GitHub.

<https://github.com/biigle/largo/issues/66>

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>

Is there a way to download the photos from the annotation catalog of a label tree? And if there is, can we download all of them at the same time?

The annotation patches can be downloaded via the API. There is a Python community script that downloads all annotation patches with a certain label either of a whole project or of a volume. This script could be extended to download all patches accessible in the annotation catalog, too. Please open a new discussion at GitHub to get advice on the necessary changes.

<https://github.com/biigle/community-scripts/tree/master/grab-largo-patches>

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>

Is it possible to edit polygons by rotating and change the sizes of them after making the annotation?

No. Please open a new discussion at GitHub to explain your particular use case in more detail.

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>

Can you recommend Windows 10 PC software to batch converter H.265 video files to AV1 for use with BIIGLE?

No. But there is much that could be improved regarding videos in BIIGLE (e.g. upload of any codec and online conversion by BIIGLE). Please get in touch via info@biigle.de if you are interested in exploring this idea further.

Regarding the navigation of the timeline of a video, is there a way to go frame by frame through it?

Currently, no. This can only be done in a very controlled environment (i.e. the video files must be converted by BIIGLE, see question above) and with significant changes in the video annotation tool. As with most new features, the BIIGLE team currently does not have the resources for the implementation. Technical details can be found in the GitHub issue below.

<https://github.com/biigle/core/issues/433>

Through the proposed GIS integration, are you looking to make the maps within BIIGLE more interactive?

There are no plans for the implementation of more GIS features in BIIGLE. Instead, BIIGLE should provide appropriate interfaces to actual GIS software (such as the image and annotation location reports). See also the notes regarding the discussion “GIS integration” above.

Any suggestion on the best way to maintain a collaborative practical guide for BIIGLE annotations and integration with machine learning?

The guide (documentation and code) can be maintained as a GitHub repository. The repository can be published at Zenodo to get a DOI and automatic updates for new versions of the guide. The guide can also be referenced in the BIIGLE community scripts repository.

<https://github.com/biigle/community-scripts>

Are taxon changes in WoRMS automatically applied to the existing tag tree - what is the frequency?

Taxon changes are not automatically applied to a label tree. BIIGLE stores the AphiaID for each label imported from WoRMS but it is currently not used for anything (see also the discussion in the GitHub issue below). In theory, a label could be automatically updated (upon user request) using the AphiaID. Please open a new discussion at GitHub if you are interested in a continued discussion about this topic.

<https://github.com/biigle/core/issues/389>

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>

Wishlist

Could we add a feature to the filtering options to filter for different shapes (points, lines, polygons, etc)?

If this request is for Largo, please refer to the GitHub issue below. If not, please open a new discussion at GitHub to elaborate on this request.

<https://github.com/biigle/largo/issues/66>

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>

Would it be possible to export still frames from video annotations into a new project in order to use image analysis tools of BIIGLE (e.g. size measures)?

Please open a discussion at GitHub to explore this idea further.

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>

Would it be possible to filter and largo by user, rather than all annotations which have been made?

I think that it would be great if we could filter for a shape and then use the largo tool to look at those instances.

Please have a look at the GitHub issue below. Feel free to add more ideas there.

<https://github.com/biigle/largo/issues/66>

Would it be possible to add a report option that includes all still images / videos in the volume even without annotations present?

There is an existing idea to include all images and labels in the abundance report. Please contribute to the issue at GitHub if there is any missing information or you need something else.

<https://github.com/biigle/reports/issues/62>

Bulk annotate labels on selected photos (i.e., apply location name to several).

This was added as a new feature idea. Please add any relevant information there.

<https://github.com/biigle/core/issues/544>

Can we get a CSV video report containing the latitude and the longitude of each frame of a video (it seems that there is this option for image files)?

Import GPS tracks and match them to report data based on the (video) timeline.

Video metadata (including position information) can currently be uploaded to BIIGLE but is not used anywhere, yet. An idea to add/merge this metadata into reports exists (see below). Please add any relevant information there.

<https://github.com/biigle/reports/issues/92>

Display labels to identify photo names on the map module.

Please open a new discussion on GitHub to describe your use case in more detail.

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>

Import a spatial line grid overlay, to enable repeated labels, i.e., substrate/cover.

BIIGLE supports the [regular and random sampling](#) annotation modes that can be used for substrate/cover percentage estimation. A regular grid can be generated with a Python community script (see below). The grid annotations are best reviewed with the [volume label review](#) annotation mode.

<https://github.com/biigle/community-scripts/tree/master/regular-sampling-grid>

Improve image and annotation exports to help programmers with analysis (AI).

BIIGLE provides the machine-readable CSV and COCO annotation reports. Please open a new discussion at GitHub to propose different formats.

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>

Clone a project to do multiple annotations on a volume ('collections' concept).

A student is currently working on a "clone volume" feature (see below) which will be released in the next weeks/months. If this does not fit to your use case, please open a new discussion at GitHub to elaborate.

<https://github.com/biigle/core/issues/442>

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>

Be able to calibrate the image size (e.g.,: 4298 px = 44 cm).

Image scale information can be uploaded as [metadata](#) (area). The area metadata attribute stores the area in m² of the whole image. BIIGLE assumes square pixels, so if 4298 px = 44 cm and an image has 6720 × 4480 px then the image area is $(0.44 \text{ m}/4298 \text{ px})^2 * 6720 \text{ px} * 4480 \text{ px} = 0.316 \text{ m}^2$. This process can be automated with [laser point detection](#) and manually set laser points (since usually the px-to-cm ratio is different for each image). Feel free to open a new discussion at GitHub if this needs further discussion.

<https://github.com/orgs/biigle/discussions>